

ELASTIC BEHAVIOR AND DAMAGE OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this research is to investigate the elastic properties and damage behavior of three-dimensional woven fabric composites. Transformed stiffness and compliance matrices have been obtained in closed-form expressions for orthotropic materials. Introduced are three *orthotropic constants* which enable the transformation to be greatly simplified. A deformation model has been established based on the force equilibrium of a slice of a fabric. Two three-dimensional woven fabrics with different weaving structures and yarn cross-sections are examined. Experiments have been conducted for three-axis fabrics. The analytical results agree well with experimental data. The damage due to flexural loads has been observed. It is found that the addition of the through-the-thickness yarns can cause defeats around the yarns. Being the crack initiators, these defeats can be detrimental to the in-plane properties.

INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional (3-D) textile composites are a unique class of materials, produced by impregnating matrix materials into fabric preforms to hold multidirectional yarns together. In comparison with two-dimensional laminated structures, textile composites based on 3-D preforms offer unique transverse properties [1,2]. As a result of the reinforcing fibers in the through-the-thickness direction, the transverse properties—including strength, stiffness, and fracture toughness—can be effectively enhanced. Therefore, these composites are essentially free from delamination and edge effects, which are often serious problems in laminated composites; consequently, they are especially suitable for multidirectional load-bearing applications [3-5]. Because of the direction dependence of composite properties, it is important to understand the response characteristics of preform architecture. This understanding can help designers to make the best use of the potential these composites offer. With the great diversity of preform architecture, however, determining the optimal condition for composite behavior by extensive

experiments could be impractical. Therefore, learning to design the preforms based upon theoretical analysis becomes essential in initial design phases.

Compared with laminated composites, 3-D textile composites are significantly more complex in terms of design and analysis. Besides those related to fiber/interface/matrix microstructures, the design parameters may include yarn size, yarn orientation, yarn volume fraction, and yarn interlacing patterns. Furthermore, the composites are three-dimensionally inhomogeneous from both the material and geometrical points of view. Thus, it is often difficult to analytically determine the material behavior and to optimize the composites through the control of these parameters. It is therefore the goal of this paper to develop a methodology for predicting linear elastic properties of the composites.

THREE-DIMENSIONAL TRANSFORMATION

Yarns are the basic building elements to assemble textile composites, and the ability to understand the fundamental behavior of a fiber yarn is essential to the resulting composite performance. To represent the yarn principal material directions, the symbols 1, 2, and 3 are used. The symbol 3 is designated to be the fiber direction, and 1 and 2 are the transverse directions, as shown in Figure 1.

The stiffness and compliance matrices of a material are of 6 by 6 and are denoted as $[Q]$ and $[S]$, respectively, for the 1-2-3 systems and $[\bar{Q}]$ and $[\bar{S}]$ for the x-y-z systems. There are a total of five independent material constants in the matrices for transversely isotropic materials, and nine for orthotropic ones.

For a spatially oriented fiber yarn, the orientation can be generally described by three angles θ , ϕ and ω as depicted in Figure 1. In this paper, the barred symbols refer to the x-y-z systems, unless otherwise noted.

Figure 1 Three-dimensional rotation of an orthotropic element

Employing the basic elastic relations, the $[\bar{\mathbf{Q}}]$ and $[\bar{\mathbf{S}}]$ for the x-y-z system can be proven to be [6-7] as following

$$\begin{aligned} [\bar{\mathbf{Q}}] &= [\mathbf{T}]^{-1}[\mathbf{Q}][\mathbf{R}][\mathbf{T}][\mathbf{R}]^{-1} \\ [\bar{\mathbf{S}}] &= [\mathbf{R}][\mathbf{T}]^{-1}[\mathbf{R}]^{-1}[\mathbf{S}][\mathbf{T}] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the matrix $[\mathbf{T}]$ is the stress transformation matrix. All matrices in Equation (1) are of 6 by 6, and the $[\mathbf{R}]$ is a 6 by 6 diagonal matrix with the diagonal terms being $\{1,1,1,2,2,2\}$.

Equations (1) can be easily evaluated based on numerical computations if all Q_{ij} and the angles are given numerically. Nevertheless, it has been known that closed-form expressions provide not only an easier way to obtain numerical results but also an explicit symbolic solution rendering analysis and design more efficient. To this end, we find that the following constants are crucial

$$\begin{aligned} K_1 &= Q_{22} + Q_{33} - 2Q_{23} - 4Q_{44}, & W_3 &= S_{22} + S_{33} - 2S_{12} - S_{66} \\ K_2 &= Q_{33} + Q_{11} - 2Q_{13} - 4Q_{55}, & W_3 &= S_{33} + S_{11} - 2S_{12} - S_{66} \\ K_3 &= Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}, & W_3 &= S_{11} + S_{22} - 2S_{12} - S_{66} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

It is clear that K's and W's are symmetric with respect to axes 1, 2, and 3. Physically, they might be interpreted as *deviations* from an isotropic medium since $K_1 = K_2 = K_3 = 0$, and $W_1 = W_2 = W_3 = 0$ for an isotropic medium.

Accordingly, rearranging the expanded \bar{Q}_{ij} and \bar{S}_{ij} and applying K's and W's, one finds the following results for \bar{Q}_{ij} and \bar{S}_{ij} :

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{Q}_{11} &= Q_{11}(mpr - ns)^2 + Q_{22}(mps + nr)^2 + Q_{33}m^2q^2 - K_1m^2q^2(mps + nr)^2 - K_2m^2q^2(mpr - ns)^2 \\ &\quad - K_3(mpr - ns)^2(mps + nr)^2 \\ \bar{Q}_{12} &= Q_{12}p^2 + Q_{13}q^2s^2 + Q_{23}q^2r^2 + K_1mnq^2(mps + nr)(mr - nps) + K_2mnq^2(ns - mpr)(ms \\ &\quad + npr) + K_3(mpr - ns)(ms + npr)(mps + nr)(mr - nps) \\ \bar{S}_{11} &= S_{11}(mpr - ns)^2 + S_{22}(mps + nr)^2 + S_{33}m^2q^2 - W_1m^2q^2(mps + nr)^2 \\ &\quad - W_2m^2q^2(mpr - ns)^2 - W_3(mpr - ns)^2(mps + nr)^2 \\ \bar{S}_{12} &= S_{12}p^2 + S_{13}q^2s^2 + S_{23}q^2r^2 + W_1mnq^2(mps + nr)(mr - nps) \\ &\quad + W_2mnq^2(ns - mpr)(ms + npr) + W_3(mpr - ns)(ms + npr)(mps + nr)(mr - nps) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $m=\cos(\theta)$, $n=\sin(\theta)$, $p=\cos(\phi)$, and $q=\sin(\phi)$, $r=\cos(\omega)$, and $s=\sin(\omega)$. It has been shown that all \bar{Q}_{ij} and \bar{S}_{ij} can be expressed by six terms as Eqn.(4) indicated. The detailed \bar{Q}_{ij} and \bar{S}_{ij} have been listed in Refs.[6,7].

THREE-DIMENSIONAL WOVEN FABRICS

Two fabrics are examined in this paper. They are termed 3D/3a and 3D/5a, in which "D" means dimension and "a" means axes. The axial yarns are selected in parallel with the z-direction; the xy-plane, where the weaving yarns lay, is termed the *weaving plane*. The total yarn volume fraction in a fabric is denoted V_y . The matrix in this space is termed the *interyarn matrix*. Consequently, the interyarn matrix volume fraction is equal to $1 - V_y$ if the interyarn space is void-free.

Figure 2 illustrates a 3D/3a woven fabric constructed by one set of axial yarns and two sets of weaving yarns; they are mutually perpendicular. The axial yarns are circular and the weaving yarns cross-sections are assumed to be elliptical. The 3D/5a fabric is the addition of two off-axis weaving yarns oriented $+45^\circ$ and -45° in the weaving planes to a 3D/3a fabric, as illustrated in Figure 3. Gaps exist in between axial and weaving yarns. In consideration of fabrication processes in which contiguous weaving yarns are normally very tight, it is assumed that there is no gap in between contiguous weaving yarns. The space allocated for the axial yarn is denoted as d_a and the axial yarn diameter is d_{ay} .

THREE-DIMENSIONAL ELASTICITY ANALYSIS

Due to yarn architecture and material inhomogeneity, the stress and strain distributions in 3-D textile composites can be very complex. It is unlikely that an exact elasticity solution satisfying all equilibrium and boundary conditions can be obtained. Therefore, simplification on the deformation relations must be made in order for the theoretical analysis to be performed.

Fig.2 The 3D/3a fabric

Fig.3 The 3D/5a fabric

The studied case of fabric stacking is called Iso-Phase Mode, assuming that all unit cells to construct a composite are placed perfectly in the same relative positions [5,7]. Based upon this, a composite cross-section has ideally repetitive patterns. The deformation, stress, and strain distribution are presumed to be repetitive for all cells. Hence, each unit cell shares identical loads, which must be in equilibrium with externally applied loads. To satisfy displacement compatibility, it is further assumed that any section originally flat prior to loading remains flat after deformation [5,7]. As a consequence, the strains vary only along the associated direction—i.e., $\epsilon_x \equiv \epsilon_x(x)$, $\epsilon_y \equiv \epsilon_y(y)$, $\epsilon_z \equiv \epsilon_z(z)$, $\gamma_{yz} \equiv \gamma_{yz}(y)$, $\gamma_{zx} \equiv \gamma_{zx}(z)$, and $\gamma_{xy} \equiv \gamma_{xy}(x)$. Knowing stresses are dominated by their corresponding strains; the contributions of the other stresses are then approximated by

$$\sigma_{xx}^{(k)} = \bar{Q}_{11}^{(k)} \epsilon_x(x) + \bar{Q}_{12}^{(k)} \bar{\epsilon}_y + \bar{Q}_{13}^{(k)} \bar{\epsilon}_z + \bar{Q}_{14}^{(k)} \bar{\gamma}_{yz} + \bar{Q}_{15}^{(k)} \bar{\gamma}_{zx} + \bar{Q}_{16}^{(k)} \bar{\gamma}_{xy} \quad (5)$$

where the superscript (k) is an index for material constituent elements within a cross-section; the constituent elements can be axial yarns, weaving yarns, and the interyarn matrix. The barred strains in the equation stand for average strains.

Based on the equilibrium condition for a 'slice' of the fabric in the x-direction, we have the relations between $\epsilon_x(x)$ and F_{xx} , the externally applied normal forces. Using the equation, one can result in the following stiffness for overall composite behavior

$$Q_{ij}^c = \int_0^{L_x} \frac{\sum_k A_x^{(k)}(x) \bar{Q}_{ij}^{(k)}}{\sum_k A_x^{(k)}(x) \bar{Q}_{ii}^{(k)}} dx \left(\int_0^{L_x} \frac{L_y L_z}{\sum_k A_x^{(k)}(x) \bar{Q}_{ii}^{(k)}} dx \right)^{-1} \quad \text{for } i=1,6 \quad (6)$$

where j is an index ranging from 1 to 6, and k is the material index ranging from 1 to the number of constituent elements. Similar expressions can be obtained for i=2, 3, 4 and 5 [7]. Once the stiffness matrix $[Q^c]$ is known, the inversion of the matrix yields the composite compliance matrix $[S^c]$ and from which the composite elastic constants can therefore be obtained.

EXPERIMENTS

The 3D/3a woven fabrics have been fabricated for the experimentation. The axial yarns are of 24K carbon yarns and the weaving yarns are of 12K, in which K stands for 1000 fibers. The distances between two axial yarns are 6mm and 8mm, respectively, for two types of specimens. After the preforms were made, a Resin-Transfer-Molding process was applied. Care must be taken in infiltrating the epoxy resin so that high degree of wetting can be obtained. The epoxy was the Ciba Geigy 260, and hardener was Ciba Geigy 976. A standard curing process provided by Ciba Geigy was applied. The tests included tensile, compressive, three-point flexural, short-beam tests. Since there is a lack of standards for three-dimensional textile composites, the ASTM standards [8], originally designed for planar laminated composites, were followed.

In each test, the elastic moduli were recorded from the initial linear part of the load-deflection curves. The morphology of fractured surfaces has been recorded using optical and scanning electronic micrographs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numerical calculations for the composite elastic constants have been carried out for the graphite/epoxy system. The following typical material constants are used: $E_3 = 163.4$ GPa, $E_1 = 11.9$ GPa, $G_{13} = 6.5$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.4$, $\nu_{13} = 0.3$ for the fiber yarn, and $E_m = 4.5$ GPa, $\nu_m = 0.4$ for the interyarn matrix. The yarn is assumed to be transversely isotropic and the interyarn matrix to be isotropic. The axial and weaving yarns are of 24K and 12K, respectively. The calculated yarn volume fractions are shown in Figure 4. As the elliptical weaving yarn becomes slender, the V_y increases. In both fabrics, yarn configurations are symmetric in the xy -plane, and the resulting composite properties associated with the x direction should be identical to those associated with the y direction—i.e., $E_x = E_y$, $G_{xz} = G_{yz}$, and $\nu_{xz} = \nu_{yz}$.

The effect of weaving yarn shape (d_{w1}/d_{w2}) on the E_z and E_x of the composite are shown in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. As the ratio increases, both moduli increase. However, it is indicated that E_z is almost irrelevant to the weaving yarn shape, since the changing of the shape virtually does not influence the axial yarn volume fraction which dominates E_z . On the other hand, the shape is critical to the weaving plane modulus E_x . As the weaving yarn becomes thinner or the d_{w1}/d_{w2} ratio becomes larger, the E_x increases significantly. Both figures also show that shorter axial yarn distance results in higher elastic moduli for both E_z and E_x . The experimental results are indicated in Figure 6 for 6mm and 8mm cases. The predicted values are slightly lower; nevertheless, both correlate well. The results for the predicted G_{xy} are listed in Figure 7. Due to two off-axis yarns, the weaving plane shear modulus is notably enhanced.

The fracture surface of a typical flexure test is shown in Figure 8. It was found that the cracks initiated from the tensile (bottom) side of the specimens. The figure also indicates that the defects around the axial yarns are the causes for crack initiation as well as for crack propagation. The crack path usually travels along either weaving or axial yarn interfaces. Therefore, to strengthen the composite, better bonding in between yarns and matrix is crucial.

CONCLUSIONS

Three-dimensional stiffness and compliance transformations of an orthotropic material have been obtained in closed-form expressions. Two 3-D woven fabrics have been examined: the 3D/3a and 3D/5a. The yarn volume fraction for each fabric has been evaluated, indicating that the fraction increases as the weaving yarns are more slender. The Young's moduli for the fabric composites have been obtained, and it is found that E_z , the axial direction modulus, is dominated by the axial yarn and is almost independent of the weaving yarn shape. The weaving plane modulus, E_x , is increases with the aspect ratio of the weaving yarn. It has been shown that

weaving shear modulus are greatly enhanced by off-axis yarns. The correlation between the predicted elastic moduli and experiments is quite well. The damage in the composite due to tensile and flexure tests is mainly initiated from the defects around the transverse yarns, indicating that while the yarns are effectively reinforcing the transverse properties, their negative effects on the in-plane strength/stiffness should be an important factor to be considered in composite design.

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Fig.4 Yarn volume fraction against the aspect ratio

Fig.5 The E_z against the dw_1/dw_2 ratio

Fig.6 The E_x against the dw_1/dw_2 ratio

Fig.7 The G_{xy} for the 3D/3a and 3D/5a composites

Fig.8 Cracking in the tensile side of a 3D/3a specimen under flexural load